

Metrics for Evaluating Accessibility of Research to Indigenous Communities

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Positionality

This short statement was led by non-Indigenous researchers in collaboration with an Indigenous scholar. An T. Nguyen is an immigrant from Vietnam and US-university trained Geophysicist and Physical Oceanographer with research specialty in Arctic Ocean modeling and data-model synthesis. Margaret Rudolf is an Inupiaq scholar and postdoctoral researcher at the University of Alaska Fairbanks (UAF). This short statement is partially based on Margaret Rudolf's work, currently in preparation for a journal article, on evaluation metrics for supporting Alaska Indigenous communities' resilience. Kirstin Schulz is a Western-Europe-trained physical oceanographer who specializes in ocean turbulence observations and processes in the polar regions. Emily Lescak is a biologist by training. She is the Research Coordinator for the International Arctic Research Center at UAF and has been project coordinator for the Research Networking Activity for Sustained, Coordinated Observations of Arctic Change (RNA CoObs) for the last two years. Noor Johnson is the descendent of European settlers to North America; she has trained as a cultural and environmental anthropologist and leads the Exchange for Local Observations and Knowledge of the Arctic (ELOKA). We, as members of the RNA CoObs team, are sharing what we learned and discussed through our project RNA CoObs. We are not speaking for Indigenous Peoples. For Indigenous voices, it is important to keep looking toward Indigenous leaders in Arctic research such as ICC (2021), Naalakkersuisut (2022), Kawerak (2024), and ITK (2018). From our positionality, we are sharing what we have learned and plan to implement in our future work, as a means to co-learn and push the Arctic observing field forward in regard to engaged research with Arctic Indigenous Peoples.

Introduction

All aspects of the research process fundamentally need to be accessible to Indigenous Peoples for them to be able to participate in and/or benefit from it. In this note, we discuss a set of metrics for use to evaluate accessibility across a project's *Process*, *Outcomes*, and *Impacts* [Rudolf et al., 2023, 2024, 2025]. *Process* includes the research design, implementation, activities, and tangible products/outputs. *Outcomes* include achievement of project goals, individual uses, actions, and additional short-term aspects that are tied directly to the project. *Impacts* refer to societal and sustained institutional changes beyond the project's lifetime. Scopes of evaluation span all facets of accessibility including

infrastructure, non-proprietary hardware and software, information dissemination and funding.

Infrastructure

A phrase often mentioned is, “Meeting people where they are at” in the context of location and relevance. In this context, it implies that throughout the *Process*, a research project’s design and implementation should incorporate innovative approaches to utilize, maximize, and/or build upon available community capacity on the ground for improved technology, tools, language, and infrastructure in communities (Yoo et al., 2021).

The word **Infrastructure** includes roads and broadband networks as well as “Natural” and “Indigenous” components which we discuss further below. An example of success in broadband network accessibility is from an infrastructure project which resulted in the inception of the Southern California Tribal Digital Village Network (Yoo et al., 2021). In that project, the building of a supercomputer required access to Tribal land in Southern California, and Indigenous leaders in the involved region, through innovative thinking, design, and implementation, devised an approach with allied academics to gain federal discounted rates to build internet infrastructure. Such projects not only improved broadband data access but also infrastructure capability. The successful outcomes include a new highspeed internet network built for and maintained by Indigenous People in California. The impacts included benefits associated with improved connectivities such as improved health, education, and social networking (Stotz et al., 2021, Yoo et al. 2021), job creation with Indigenous people working for the community, as well as guidance for successful workaround approaches with allies in future projects. The improved capacity also strengthens self-governance and self-determination.

Ebhuoma (2024) defines natural Infrastructure in the context of environment or land resources. Toward accessibility, a research project can secure funding for Indigenous partners and leaders to co-design cost-effective methods for data collection to sustain access and build capacities for natural infrastructure while accounting for improved well-being. The potential outcomes of such careful design can include “cost-effectiveness of different conservation strategies which may yield the highest return on investment regarding both ecological outcomes and community wellbeing” (Ebhuoma, 2024). The long-term impacts of such approaches include enhanced economic and political values of Indigenous Knowledge System (IKS) in “the protection of natural infrastructure in the face of a rapidly changing climate” and in shaping policies.

Schaeffer (2025) discussed the needs for improved access to and maintenance of “Indigenous infrastructure”. These include, e.g., fish camps for community gathering or traditional trails used for hunting, all of which strengthen communities and Indigenous lifeways. As climate change impacts all facets of life in the communities, in addition to roads, Schaeffer (2025) advocated for research that can strategize funding, as part of design and implementation, toward sustaining access to this infrastructure. Through careful design, Indigenous communities can lead monitoring and data analysis in contexts relevant to local priorities. The outcome can be a transformative research process toward long-term sustainable monitoring efforts identified by and serving local/circum-Arctic communities. In addition, long term impacts can include the sustainability of Indigenous ways of living in the changing Arctic.

Proprietary Restrictions

Beyond infrastructure, data, software, and hardware should be free of **proprietary restrictions** to facilitate accessibility. Projects should employ non-proprietary tools, empower Indigenous-led software application development (e.g. through the Indigenous Social Network SIKU, siku.org) and hardware operations (e.g. the Tribal owned and operated broadband Tribal Digital Village Network, Yoo et al., 2021), and follow the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and CARE (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics) principles to ensure data are interoperable (Wilkinson et al., 2016) while protecting Indigenous rights and interests (Carroll et al., 2020). A major benefit of universally-available hardware is the ability to repair equipment / tools much more quickly without having to wait for proprietary equipment to ship or a technician to come; this is particularly important for remote communities. Thus, use of open-source, universal-designed software and hardware enables researchers and community members to contribute to the building and maintenance of equipment during and after the lifetime of the project. Practicing the FAIR principles promotes greater adoption of open science practices and increases applicability, use and exchange of data and Indigenous knowledge, which leads to increased knowledge gain and elevates Indigenous Knowledge Systems. The pairing of FAIR with CARE principles safe-guard data ownership, narrative and usage towards empowering Indigenous Peoples, their cultures, communities, and territories. Research projects which encourage users of Indigenous data to “Be FAIR and CARE” thus empower ethically responsible shared data ownership and stewardship, which in turn, strengthen Indigenous Peoples’ data innovation, governance, self-determination and sovereignty (Carroll et al., 2020).

The *Nalaquq* (“it is found”) co-production framework (Gleason et al., 2023) provides guidance for projects seeking to monitor climate change using digital technologies such as drones, with emphasis on community access to infrastructure, training, software, hardware, and data/result communication and sharing. Their recommendations for success include designing sensor networks that can operate on low bandwidth internet and in harsh environments, employing decolonization methods to meaningfully monitor the environment in ways that elevate and respect Indigenous Knowledges and Practice and with community input and oversight, communicating data/results through simple language and visualization, and using local storage of digital data for community access and protection of data sovereignty. As a model, they outlined an Indigenous-tested and -approved environmental “toolkit” at an affordable price (e.g., <\$5000) that can be easily transported using local transportation means and enable community members to collect data in limited broadband access at sites chosen with input from Elders. Some examples of successful outcomes and associated impacts, through applying the *Nalaquq* framework, include drone-derived salmon surveys to aid community negotiation of fishing quotas, maps of coastal erosion in Indigenous lands to estimate monetary impact, and local development of software used in search and rescue using drone data and machine-learning techniques. Other long term impacts include data ownership and larger community engagements. An example of these long term impacts was the community-based Nunalleq Archaeological Project (Hillerdal et al., 2023). The project started in 2007 when locals in a Yup’ik village of Quinhagak in southwest Alaska discovered pre-contact archeological artifacts and sought out a collaboration with archeologists from the University of Aberdeen, Scotland. Due to the village’s remote location and lack of infrastructure and resources, the artifacts excavated from the ancestral site Nunalleq were originally planned to be archived in a museum either in Fairbanks or Anchorage. The extensive collaboration between 2007-2018 built local capacity and expertise and has led to the establishment in 2018 of the Nunalleq Culture and Archaeology Center where the artifacts are now archived under guardianship of the descendant

community. The center serves as a site for cultural heritage and brings together Yup'ik communities and results in regional and world-wide connections beyond Quinhagak [Hillerdal et al., 2023].

Dissemination of information

Information dissemination must aim to be accessible in language, form and timing. Information here refers to data, results, reports and outputs. In communication, there is a need for having easy-to-understand content in local and non-jargon plain language. This could mean hiring Indigenous-led communicators, artists, and story-tellers, such that data providers have a better sense of how their data contributed to knowledge gain (Rupp et al., 2024). As an example, for a project measuring permafrost, results of “permafrost projections, temperature projections, and other information can [...] be returned alongside accompanying interpretive text to assist in understanding or provide cautionary considerations” (Rupp et al., 2024).

Flexible with high ease-of-access formats familiar and/or most effective for community distribution can include e.g., social media posts on Facebook and other platforms, PDFs, maps, and Indigenous-owned newsletters. Examples include sending maps, data, and results to communities using a non-academic medium. Examples include the Alaska Arctic Observatory & Knowledge Hub (AAOKH, <https://arctic-aok.org/>) newsletter, the Indigenous Knowledge App Siku (<https://siku.org/>) in Inuit language, Facebook posts and radio programs, and the Strait Sciences series at Northwest Campus in the University of Alaska Fairbanks (<https://www.uaf.edu/nwc/outreach/strait-science.php>) which promote understanding between citizens of the Bering Strait region and the researchers who frequent the Seward Peninsula. By utilizing these existing Indigenous platforms for communication and dissemination, researchers can support and elevate communication methods that have a track record of effective Indigenous engagement. One example of this is the Local Environmental Observer (LEO, Mosites et al., 2018), a global social media network established by the Alaska Native Tribal Health Consortium in 2012 that recruits Arctic citizens to post environmental observations such as food sources, wild fire smoke, coastal erosion and thawing permafrost on social media platforms. These observations connect hard-to-reach local and Arctic-wide community members to each other and to healthcare and environmental experts, and lead to enhanced connectivities and protection of Arctic residents' health (Mosites et al., 2018).

When design maximizes existing infrastructure and networking, information can be updated frequently, relayed promptly, and stored in multiple ways to best suit the needs and capacities of partners. Prompt data delivery to Tribal and State decision-makers can level the data access playing field in moments of critical response (Garron et al., 2022), which, in turn, leads to increased community participation and ownership of research and data monitoring, and ultimately decision making supporting sovereignty. An example is described in Garron et al. (2022) on prompt connection from academia to response: “At the conclusion of the storm, the Native Village of Unalakleet (NVU) Uncrew Aircraft Systems (UAS) team deployed immediately to collect post-storm assessments of critical infrastructure in the community which were then processed as orthomosaics and PDFs for delivery to the state emergency operations center within 24-hours of collection and provided to local leaders for immediate decision-making for the community's storm response” (Garron et al., 2022).

Knowledge Translation

Besides the translation of research data, methods, and results into local languages, there is an additional nuanced layer of “**Knowledge Translation**” (KT). Often employed in the context of health research, KT can have different meanings depending on positionality (Legault et al., 2025 and references therein). Ninomiya et al. (2022) defined KT as “locally developed systems” such as local Indigenous’ guidance that can “link local cultural relevance and research knowledge to sharing what we [Indigenous Peoples] know about living a good life.” A key part of an effective Knowledge Translation strategy is the involvement of community members, especially Elders, Knowledge Keepers and grandparents, and production of materials and tools with cultural references and explanations using local and Indigenous languages (Ninomiya et al., 2022, Legault et al., 2025). Outcomes thus can be enhanced “direct engagement with local communities, locally developed system(s) that link(s) local culture and research knowledge to Indigenous way of conducting research within Indigenous knowledge systems and contexts”. Long-term impacts of knowledge exchange can be that research procedures and results are shaped in a way that “honours and respects the Indigenous contextually relevant ways of knowing and doing research”, following guidance that “within Indigenous knowledge systems and contexts, research without practical relevance or application has no merit or value.” (Ninomiya et al., 2022).

Funding

Last but potentially most importantly is accessibility to **Funding**. Here we are referring not only to funding resources for Indigenous partners but also to fund Indigenous representatives in leadership roles and Indigenous-led research. Representative leaders can effectively communicate with communities, make decisions or have an equal voice during the planning/designing phase, decision-making, and dissemination of results processes. In addition, they serve as mentors for early-career professionals, Indigenous members, and boundary spanners within the team, thus empowering a new generation of Indigenous and non-Indigenous allied leadership. Securing funding for multiple Indigenous leaders or representatives also ensures the project has a critical mass of Indigenous People for relationship building and decision making. Starting from the planning phase, when funding can be secured for Indigenous-led research (ITK 2018), there is a much greater chance for community participation utilizing Indigenous methods and knowledge to expand existing and/or establishing new relationships with communities, address the community's priorities and have outcomes that will directly benefit the communities. The long-term impacts can include expansion of existing or new relationships with communities and Indigenous leaders, engaging and training a new generation of Indigenous and non-Indigenous allied leadership, and forming pathways for more Indigenous-led research within existing funding structures.

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